

Awareness and Acceptance of Hydra-form Brick Blocks for Teachers' Housing in Bwari Area Council, Abuja

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Abstract

Nigeria's persistent housing deficit, driven by rapid urbanization, high construction costs, and systemic policy gaps, has left many public servants, particularly teachers, unable to access adequate and affordable housing. This study explored the potential of Hydra-form brick blocks as a sustainable, cost-effective alternative to conventional sandcrete blocks for addressing housing needs in Bwari Area Council of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. The research assessed teachers' awareness and perception of Hydra-form bricks and identified the key factors influencing their acceptance. A mixed-methods approach was employed, using questionnaires, observations, and reconnaissance surveys across eleven randomly selected public schools, with a sample of 226 teachers representing about 60% of the teacher population. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, weighted mean scores, and Chi-square tests. Findings revealed that 62.5% of teachers were aware of Hydra-form bricks, with traditional and digital media being the main sources of information, while familiarity levels remained moderate (mean = 3.4). Environmental sustainability (47.8%), durability (20.3%), and cost-effectiveness (18.1%) were the most recognized benefits, though misconceptions and lack of practical exposure limited broader acceptance. Preference for Hydra-form housing was high, with 79.7% agreeing they would live in such houses, and 49.6% expressing definite willingness to invest if prices matched those of traditional sandcrete houses. Durability, sustainability, and comfort were identified as the most critical factors shaping acceptance, while cost and government incentives played secondary roles. The Chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 17.54, p = 0.00015$) confirmed a strong statistically significant association between preference and willingness to invest. The study concludes that Hydra-form bricks present a viable solution for sustainable teacher housing in Bwari, provided that awareness gaps, labor availability concerns, and trust issues are addressed. It recommends intensified sensitization through pilot projects, training programs for local artisans, supportive housing policies, and government-backed incentives such as subsidies or affordable financing. Continuous

research and performance monitoring are further suggested to strengthen confidence and facilitate wider adoption of Hydra-form bricks as part of Nigeria's sustainable housing strategy.

Keywords: Hydra-form brick blocks, Affordable housing, Teachers' housing, Environmental Sustainability, building materials.

1.1 Introduction

Housing is a fundamental driver of national development, influencing quality of life, health outcomes, and socio-economic well-being (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). In Nigeria, rapid urbanization and population growth have exacerbated the housing deficit, posing significant challenges for low- and middle-income earners, particularly in urban and peri-urban areas (Adepoju & Oni, 2021). To address this challenge, mass housing initiatives have become a key strategy; however, their long-term sustainability depends largely on the choice of building materials (Olubunmiet *al.*, 2019). Hydra-form brick blocks, produced from compressed laterite soil stabilized with cement, are increasingly recognized as a sustainable and cost-effective alternative to conventional sandcrete blocks (Ogunbode *et al.*, 2021). These bricks offer several advantages, including affordability, durability, reduced cement dependency, and superior thermal insulation (Mabogunje, 2021). Beyond their technical benefits, the adoption of Hydra-form bricks relies heavily on awareness and acceptance among potential users, especially in contexts where conventional materials dominate (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 2023).

Teachers represent a critical low—medium class workforce in national development but often encounter unique housing challenges. In peri-urban areas such as Bwari Area Council, Abuja, rising population pressures and limited infrastructure further constrain access to affordable and adequate housing

(Okere, 2020; Akinmoladun and Adegboye, 2022). Exploring teachers' perception of Hydra-form brick blocks is therefore essential in determining the feasibility of integrating this technology into housing schemes designed for low and middle income class. Prior studies suggest that social perception, awareness levels, and socio-economic factors strongly influence the adoption of innovative building materials (Olawuyi *et al.*, 2022).

Hydra-form blocks, under reference is compressed earth blocks (CEBs) which have been successfully applied in other regions, limited research exists on their use in Nigeria for specialized housing projects such as teachers' quarters (Musa and Sani, 2020). In particular, there is little understanding of teachers' awareness of Hydra-form blocks and how factors such as cost, comfort, durability, environmental benefits, and social acceptability affect their willingness to adopt the material (Adedeji and Abiola, 2020; Ayinde, 2022). Misconceptions or lack of familiarity may further discourage their uptake (Ezeh, 2019). Given Nigeria's persistent housing deficit and the high cost of conventional building materials, Hydra-form bricks present a promising alternative that is locally sourced, sustainable, and affordable (Abubakar and Sulaimon, 2020; Ogunmakin, 2021). However, the success of this solution depends on understanding the behavioral and socio-economic factors that shape its acceptance.

Accordingly, this study seeks to assess the level of awareness and perception of Hydra-form brick blocks among teachers in Bwari Area Council and to identify the key factors influencing their acceptance. By doing so, the study contributes to knowledge on the socio-behavioral dynamics necessary for mainstreaming sustainable building technologies in Nigeria's housing sector.

1.2 Study Area

This study was conducted in Bwari Area Council, one of the six area councils of the Federal Capital Territory (F.C.T.), Abuja, Nigeria. Bwari lies in the northwestern part of the F.C.T. and shares boundaries with Kaduna State to the north, Niger State to the west, and Abuja Municipal and Gwagwalada Area Councils to the south and east. The Council serves as both an administrative and educational hub, hosting several key institutions such as the Nigerian Law School and Baze University. According to the National Population Commission (2016 estimates), Bwari has a population of over 250,000 people, with rapid annual growth driven by urban expansion and migration into the F.C.T. The area is predominantly peri-urban, with a mix of rural settlements and developing urban centers. Its residents are largely civil servants, artisans, traders, and

students, many of whom fall within the low- to middle-income categories.

Like many fast-growing peri-urban areas in Nigeria, Bwari faces pressing housing challenges, including rising construction costs, shortage of affordable housing, and numerous abandoned or incomplete projects. These challenges limit access to adequate housing for public servants, low income earners, including teachers, who play a critical role in the area's development. Given these circumstances, Bwari provides a suitable context for evaluating the potential of Hydra-form brick blocks as a cost-efficient and sustainable building material. Their adoption could reduce overall construction costs, improve housing accessibility for low-income earners, and stimulate local employment opportunities through the use of locally available laterite soils. By addressing both housing and livelihood concerns. The study area presents an ideal setting for assessing the socio-economic relevance and acceptance of Hydra-form blocks in mass housing schemes.

2.1. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on mass housing shows that the concept emerged as a response to rapid industrialization, urbanization and post-war reconstruction efforts in the twentieth century. Initially, the ideology of mass housing emphasized scale and standardization as a means of producing large numbers of housing units quickly and at minimal cost (Muazu & Oktay, 2011). This approach was rooted in the belief that mass-produced housing could address the urgent shelter needs of growing populations. However, over time, the ideology evolved to reflect broader concerns about quality, social integration, and sustainability. Scholars now argue that modern mass housing must not only provide physical shelter but also support community well-being, enhance energy efficiency, and align with environmental goals (Oladimeji *et al.*, 2024; Odoyi and Riekkinen, 2022).

The development of mass housing has followed different trajectories in developed and developing countries. In Europe and North America, early public housing projects were heavily criticized for monotony, social segregation, and eventual decline in quality. These criticisms triggered reforms that shifted attention towards mixed-income, energy-efficient, and socially inclusive housing models (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). In contrast, developing countries often grapple with more fundamental constraints, including limited financing options, weak

Figure 1.1: [Map of FCT, Nigeria](#)
Source: Federal Ministry of works, FCT (2024)

Nigeria presents a particularly challenging case, with its housing deficit estimated at over 20 million units (Okere, 2020). The deficit is driven by rapid urbanization, high population growth, and the high cost of construction, especially the dependence on imported materials such as cement and steel (Ikiriko and Enwin, 2023). Beyond material costs, systemic issues such as corruption, poor planning, inadequate mortgage systems, and complex land tenure arrangements further constrain affordable housing delivery (Odoyi and Riekkinen, 2022). Public servants, including teachers, are especially affected as their income levels often exclude them from the formal housing market, pushing them into informal

settlements (Akinmoladun and Adegboye, 2022). These challenges underscore the urgent need for innovative approaches that reduce costs and enhance accessibility without compromising quality.

One promising solution lies in the adoption of alternative and locally sourced building materials. Research shows that compressed stabilized earth blocks and lateritic soil blocks, including hydra-form bricks, offer significant cost savings and environmental benefits compared to conventional sand-concrete blocks (Olutoge *et al.*, 2018; Ibrahim *et al.*, 2020). Hydra-form bricks, for example, reduce dependency on cement, provide better thermal insulation, and can be produced using locally available laterite soils. This reduces construction costs while simultaneously creating employment opportunities for local communities. Studies further suggest that these

blocks meet durability and strength requirements for housing construction, making them a viable substitute for conventional materials (Enwin, and Ikiriko,2023).). However, their widespread adoption depends on overcoming barriers such as limited awareness, misconceptions about quality, and resistance to non-traditional materials (Alagbe, 2021).

Addressing Nigeria's housing challenges therefore requires a combination of material innovation, policy reform, and financial restructuring. Policy interventions are needed to provide affordable land, streamline regulatory processes, and strengthen mortgage systems that enable low-income households to access housing (Oladimeji *et al.*, 2024). Public-private partnerships and cooperative housing schemes have also been proposed as ways of reducing costs and improving efficiency. Equally important is the need for social awareness campaigns that promote acceptance of alternative building technologies, ensuring that affordability and sustainability are not hindered by negative perceptions (Alagbe, 2021).

The concept of sustainability provides an important framework for evaluating such solutions. Sustainable housing involves environmental, economic, and social dimensions. Environmentally, it emphasizes the use of eco-friendly materials, reduction of embodied energy, and promotion of thermal comfort (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2020). Economically, it focuses on cost reduction, affordability, and local job creation through the use of local resources (Olutoge *et al.*, 2018). Socially, sustainability is linked to cultural appropriateness, social inclusivity, and the overall well-being of residents (Odoyi and Riekkinen, 2022). Hydra-form blocks align well with these principles, making them an ideal candidate for sustainable housing delivery in Nigeria. Their adoption not only addresses affordability but also supports broader socio-economic and environmental objectives, reflecting a shift in housing ideology towards integrated and sustainable approaches.

3 Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-methods approach, relying on both primary and secondary data. Primary data were obtained through questionnaires, interviews, direct observations, conducted among teachers in selected public primary and secondary schools in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. Secondary data were sourced from published journals, theses, textbooks, government reports, maps, and online resources to provide contextual and supporting information. These include enrollment of teachers in all public schools in Bwari lo-

cal government and the number of schools in the area. The sampling frame consisted of teachers across salary grade levels in public schools, and using random sampling, five primary schools and six secondary schools were selected, giving a total of eleven schools. A sample size of 226 teachers, representing 60% of the total teachers' population in the area, was chosen for the study. Random sampling ensured unbiased school selection, while incidental sampling was used to distribute questionnaires to the teachers. In total, 226 questionnaires were administered, with the data collection process supplemented by interviews and field observations to capture perceptions, awareness, and acceptance of Hydra-form brick blocks as a sustainable housing material for teachers' housing.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Level of Awareness and Perception Among Teachers Regarding Hydra-form Brick Blocks

The results indicate that 62.5% of teachers were aware of Hydra-form brick blocks, while 37.5% had no prior knowledge, suggesting that although the material has gained moderate recognition within Bwari Area Council, a significant proportion of teachers remain uninformed about the material (See Fig . 4.1).

4.2 Sources of information about hydra form

When examining sources of information, traditional media accounted for 40.7%, followed by social media and internet platforms which accounted for (24.1%), government and NGO initiatives (20.0%), while friends and family source accounted for (15.2%). This highlights the continued influence of traditional media information dissemination in shaping public knowledge, which reflects the growing importance of digital platforms as a source of information (see fig 4.2).

4.3 Familiarity with the Use of Hydra-Form Brick Blocks in Construction

In terms of familiarity, the weighted analysis produced an average mean score of 3.4, slightly above neutral, showing that many respondents had some exposure to the use of Hydra-form blocks, but a substantial proportion remained either unfamiliar or only partially knowledgeable. This underscores the need for further training and awareness campaigns to bridge knowledge gaps and promote confidence in the material (Table 4.1).

Figure 4.1: Respondents' level of awareness about hydra-form brick blocks
Source: Authors Field Survey, 2025

Figure 4.2: Respondents' responses to how they first learn about hydra-form brick blocks
Source: Authors Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1 Familiarity with the Use of Hydra-Form Brick Blocks in Construction Index (FUHFBBCI)

	Very Unfamiliar (1)	Some-what Unfamiliar (2)	Neu-tral (3)	Some-what Famil-iar (4)	Very Famil-iar (5)	Total Fre- quency (f)	TWV	TWV/ f	Aver- age mean μ
<u>How familiar are you with the use of hy- dra-form brick blocks in construc-</u>	23	39	35	84	51	232	797	3.4	53.1

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

4.4. Perceived benefits of Hydra-Form Brick Blocks in Construction

When asked about the perceived benefits of Hydra-form Brick Blocks, most respondents emphasized environmental friendliness (47.8%), followed by durability (20.3%), cost-effectiveness (18.1%), and speed of construction (13.8%). The dominance of envi-

ronmental benefits indicates that ecological sustainability is widely recognized, while the relatively lower emphasis on cost and efficiency shows limited awareness of the full economic potential of Hydra-form blocks (See Fig . 4.3

Figure 4.3: Respondents’ Awareness of the Benefits of Hydra-form Brick Blocks

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

4.5 Viability of Hydra-form Brick Blocks as an alternative to conventional blocks,

The responses from the evaluation of whether Hydra-form brick blocks are a viable alternative to conventional blocks show that, 62.5% agreed, while 37.5% disagreed. This reflects a generally positive perception but also reveals persisting doubts related to availability, durability, and unfamiliarity with practical applications. Addressing these concerns through demonstration projects, policy advocacy, and technical sensitization could significantly enhance acceptance of Hydra-form brick blocks among teachers in Bwari (See Fig. 4.4)

4.6 Key Factors Influencing Teachers' Acceptance of Hydra-Form Brick Blocks

The findings reveal a generally favorable inclination toward Hydra-form brick blocks for housing construction in Bwari Area Council. When asked about their preferences for living in a house built with Hydra-form blocks compared to traditional sandcrete blocks, nearly half (47.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed; 32.3% agreed while only a small proportion of the respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed. The average weighted mean score of 4.1 confirms that most teachers expressed a positive preference towards Hydra-form housing (Table 4.2).

Figure 4.4 : Respondents' responses of hydra-form brick blocks viability
 Source: Authors' Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2: Preferences for Living in a House Built with Hydra-Form Brick Blocks

	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Neutral (3)	Agree (4)	Strongly Agree (5)	Total Frequency (f)	TWV	TWV/f	Average mean μ
"I would prefer to live in a house built with Hydra-form brick blocks over one built with traditional sandcrete blocks.	12	8	27	75	110	232	959	4.1	63.9

4.7 Reasons behind preferences for Hydra-Form Brick Blocks

The reasons behind this preference were further explored, with better insulation (37.9%) emerging as the most cited factor, followed by higher durability (31.9%),

and equally, lower initial cost (15.1%) and availability of skilled labor (15.1%). This indicates that respondents value both the performance and economic advantages of Hydra-form bricks, though

Figure 4.4: Respondents’ responses to the primary reasons for preference or lack of preference for Hydra-form brick blocks
 Source: Authors Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.3: Factors to consider in the Use of Hydra-Form Brick Blocks in Housing Index

	Not Very Important (1)	Not Important (2)	Neutral (3)	Important (4)	Very Important (5)	Total Frequency (f)	TWV	TWV/f	Average mean μ
Cost of materials	15	5	20	85	107	232	960	4.14	64.0
Durability and lifespan	0	0	0	95	137	232	1065	4.59	71.0
Availability of local materials	8	3	26	45	150	232	1022	4.41	68.13
Ease of construction and availability of labor	5	2	32	65	128	232	1005	4.33	67.0
Environmental impact and sustainability	0	0	0	97	135	232	1063	4.58	70.87
Comfort and living quality	0	0	12	95	125	232	1041	4.49	69.40
Government support or incentives	14	10	22	75	111	232	955	4.12	63.67
								30.65/7	
								4.38	

Source: Authors’ Field Survey, 2025

4.8 Factors affecting the Use of Hydra-Form Brick Blocks

When asked the respondents to rate the importance of various factors influencing their acceptance of Hydra-form blocks, respondents ranked durability and lifespan (mean = 4.59), environmental sustainability (mean = 4.58), and comfort and living

quality (mean = 4.49) as the most critical underlying factors. Factors such as availability of local materials (mean = 4.41) and ease of construction (mean = 4.33) were also rated highly, while cost of materials (mean = 4.14) and government support or incentives (mean = 4.12), though important, were relatively less influential. These results emphasize that technical and performance-related attributes outweigh purely economic or policy-driven factors in shaping ac-

4.9. Willingness to invest in Hydra-Form Brick Blocks for building construction

In terms of willingness to invest, nearly half (49.6%) of the respondents stated they would definitely invest in a Hydra-form block house if priced the same as one built with traditional sandcrete blocks, while 32.3%

[said](#) they might consider it depending on other factors. Only 18.1% preferred traditional materials regardless of price parity, suggesting that Hydra-form blocks enjoy strong potential market acceptance but still face resistance from a minority (Table 4.5).

Table 4.5 Respondents’ responses on willingness to invest in a home built with Hydra-form brick blocks if it were priced similarly to one built with traditional blocks

Study Area	Would you be willing to invest in a home built with Hydra-form brick blocks if it were priced similarly to one built with traditional blocks?			Total (Frequency)
		Freq.	%	
Selected Public Secondary Schools in Bwari Area Council, F.C.T	Yes, definitely	115	49.6	115
	Maybe, depending on other factors	75	32.3	75
	No, I would prefer traditional materials	42	18.1	42
Grand Total		232	100.0	232

4.10 The relationship between preferences and willingness to invest in Hydra-form brick houses

[To test the relationship between preference and willingness to invest](#), a Chi-square analysis was conducted, producing a statistically significant result ($\chi^2 = 17.54$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.00015$). This confirms that respondents who already prefer Hydra-form brick houses are significantly more likely to invest in them if price is not a barrier (See Table 4.6).

Table 4.6: Chi-Square Test Showing Association Between Preference for Hydra-Form Brick Block Houses and Willingness to Invest

Preference Level	Yes, definitely	Maybe	Not at all	Row Total
Agree (Agree + Strongly Agree)	115	75	10	200
Neutral / Disagree (Neutral + Disagree + Strongly Disagree)	5	10	17	32
Column Total	120	85	27	232

Chi-square value (χ^2) = 17.54, Degrees of freedom (df) = 2 p-value = 0.00015

Source: Author’s Field Survey, 2025

Overall, the analysis highlights that durability, sustainability, and comfort are the most influential factors dictating teachers' acceptance of Hydra-form brick blocks in Bwari area, Abuja. Although, cost and government incentives remain relevant, they are secondary considerations compared to performance-based attributes. Importantly, the Chi-square test confirms that preferences are strong predictors of investment willingness. These findings suggest that increasing adoption of hybrid brick blocks will depend on emphasizing the proven durability, environmental benefits, and superior comfort of Hydra-form blocks while complementing with sensitization campaigns and demonstration projects to address lingering skepticism will increase acceptability and patronage.

5. Conclusion

The study established that teachers in Bwari Area Council generally hold a favorable perception of Hydra-form brick blocks as an alternative to conventional sandcrete. Preference levels were high, with most respondents willing to live in and even invest in homes built with Hydra-form bricks, particularly when priced similarly to traditional materials. The most influential factors driving acceptance were durability, environmental sustainability, and comfort, while cost and government incentives, though relevant, played a secondary role. The Chi-square test further confirmed a strong association between preference and willingness to invest, showing that positive perceptions translate into tangible housing choices. However, lingering skepticism rooted in limited awareness, availability concerns, and unfamiliarity with practical applications suggests that wider adoption will require deliberate efforts to build trust and confidence in the technology.

6. Recommendations

In order to enhance the adoption of Hydra-form brick blocks in housing construction for teachers in Bwari Area Council, deliberate strategies must be pursued across awareness, skills development, and policy support. First, government agencies, NGOs, and construction stakeholders should intensify sensitization campaigns through demonstration projects and pilot teacher housing schemes to showcase the durability, sustainability, and comfort advantages of Hydra-form technology. Alongside this, capacity-building programs are needed to train local builders and artisans, thereby addressing concerns about the availability of skilled labor and ensuring quality workmanship. Policy frameworks should also incorporate Hydra-form blocks into affordable housing initiatives, with incentives such as subsidies, tax reliefs, or access to low-interest loans to make the technology more accessible to teachers and low-income earners. Furthermore, awareness efforts should not

only highlight the environmental and technical benefits of the material but also emphasize its cost-effectiveness and efficiency, which remain important considerations for household investment decisions. Finally, continuous research and performance monitoring are recommended to provide evidence of long-term durability and user satisfaction, thereby strengthening confidence and guiding wider adoption across the region.

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